

Evaluation of the Change of Function of the Historic Church in Nicosia; Haydarpaşa Mosque

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ABSTRACT: Historical buildings serve as important cultural assets, reflecting the past and the lifestyle of their respective eras. Their preservation is crucial, requiring continuous maintenance and appropriate repurposing. Churches, in particular, carry symbolic and historical significance, acting as monuments that transfer knowledge and culture across generations. The question of how to reuse these structures without compromising their integrity is a key issue in conservation. This study focuses on the Haydarpaşa Mosque in Nicosia, originally built as St. Catherine Church. The structure has undergone multiple functional transformations: first serving as a church, later converted into a mosque, and now functioning as an art gallery. After being used for religious purposes twice, it has taken on a cultural role. The research examines how these changes align with the building's architectural features, its integration into the urban fabric, and its suitability for different functions. The study also includes examples of churches worldwide that have been repurposed for new uses, analyzing their transformation processes. Limited to Nicosia and this specific building, the research employs qualitative methods, incorporating observations, academic literature, theses, and online resources. Additionally, local residents were surveyed to gather opinions on the current function of the structure and potential alternative uses that could benefit the public. The results, combined with literature findings, provide a comparative perspective on adaptive reuse strategies for historical buildings. The study evaluates whether the current function of the Haydarpaşa Mosque aligns with its historical and architectural characteristics while drawing parallels with similar cases. Ultimately, it highlights the importance of sustainable conservation and appropriate function assignment in preserving historical structures.

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INTRODUCTION

Cyprus' rich cultural history is observed throughout the island. The central city of Nicosia, the capital of Cyprus, is located in the main area of this rich heritage. As the capital, the city has developed along with its surroundings. The historical fabric in the center began to develop, and religious structures such as churches, monasteries, inns, and baths are among the architectural works of the historical fabric. It is said that there are more than two hundred and fifty churches in Nicosia [1].

The study focuses on the Haydarpaşa Mosque. The Haydarpaşa Mosque was originally built as a Gothic church during the Lusignan period in the 14th century. It has been described by historian Sir Harry Luke as the most elegant and perfect Gothic building in Cyprus (Manga, 2014). The building, initially named St. Catherine Church, was later modified with the addition of a minaret, mihrab, and pulpit to serve as a mosque, and it was named after Haydar Pasha, one of the commanders of the Ottoman army. In the subsequent years, the building has hosted other functions as well. In the 1990s, following restoration, the structure served for artistic activities, but it is currently not in use.

These structures in Nicosia, which reflect our culture, must be passed on to the future and should be preserved without causing harm to them. These buildings, influenced by different cultures and periods, have transitioned from religious structures to cultural buildings, from cultural buildings back to religious functions, and have served other functions over time. The changes in these functions have occurred due to the varying cultural needs of the time, and the functions required during those periods. These changes,

through maintenance and restoration, have often caused damage to the structure, and the suitability of the alterations is also debated. For example, before assigning functions such as an art gallery or library to a church, the compatibility of the building and its architectural elements with these functions should be investigated. Additionally, considering the surrounding buildings and their functions may provide insight into these decisions.

The aim of the study is to identify the changing functions of the historical church from the past to the present and the types of functions it has served. In addition to analyzing the current function of the building, the study also examines what other potential functions could be assigned to the structure without causing harm to it.

Definition of the Problem

The historic churches have high cultural value with their gothic architectural structure and magnificent appearance. Transferring these structures to the future and preserving them in their original form will reflect our history as a mirror of our past. The buildings have been subjected to deterioration due to natural disasters over time and there are many buildings that are not used by the public. These buildings are tried to be kept standing by the state through restoration processes, but the empty buildings are exposed to destruction again at the end of the day. In order to prevent this, it is proposed to give function to empty buildings, but these functions cause questions in mind.

- Would it disturb the public if the churches remained in their original form and functioned as mosques in today's conditions? (Religious building to remain a religious building)
- What can be the closest service function without destroying the original state of the churches and how is this determined?

Aim and Limitation of the Study

The historical building in Nicosia Walled City has experienced differences in function with the effect of different periods. From church function to mosque function, it has hosted different services than mosque function. The aim of the research is to investigate the functions of the historic church that have changed from past to present and to identify the types of functions it has served. The study also aims to evaluate the satisfaction with the building's current function and explore the possibilities of assigning it a new function without causing damage to the structure.

This study will cover Haydarpaşa Mosque in Nicosia Walled City.

METHODOLOGY

a. Data Collection

The data in our research were collected from primary data sources such as books, articles, theses and internet sources. Photographs were taken to see the harmony between the architectural features of the building and its current function. Among the purposive sampling methods, typical case sampling method, that is, one or more churches with the same typical case characteristics will be selected and sampled. For the new function, the questions will be conveyed by face-to-face interview and online platform method with the local people by survey method.

b. Data Collection Tools

The questions were conveyed to the public with the 4-point Likert Scale method. Information was collected by taking photographs of the current function of the building and the architectural features of the last state of the building. The survey was conducted with 30 people.

c. Data Assessment

Percentage data of the answers were calculated with Excel programme. The findings obtained were concretised in tables. While the resulting percentage data provides information about the current function of the building, the percentages of the options offered for taking a new function are given on the table and the results obtained by analysing the results are evaluated and conclusions are reached by evaluating the findings obtained.

Nicosia is the capital of the island. Since 1974, the capital has remained formally divided and is known as Lefkoşa for Turkish Cypriots and Levkosia for Greek Cypriots. Nicosia is known as the region where the historical texture began and spread, being at the heart of history. It is known that the development of significant historical monuments and structures started here. The area is recognized as the center of churches and other historical sites.

Figure 1: Map of cyprus

RE-FUNCTIONALISATION OF HISTORIC BUILDINGS

Historical buildings are considered significant cultural heritage that reflects the historical and cultural identity of a region and city. Since these structures mirror the identity of cities, they face the risk of deterioration over time, potentially disappearing gradually amidst modern buildings, leading to the loss of cultural identity. To prevent this, maintenance and restoration work are carried out on these buildings. Through the restoration process, these structures can be passed on to future generations. Restoration is defined as the process of reinforcing and slowing the deterioration of an artwork or element to preserve its historical integrity and, when necessary, return it as close as possible to its original condition (Hasol, 2005). The goal of restoration is to ensure that the historical value of a structure is preserved with minimal intervention.

There are several types of restoration. These options include:

- Reinforcement,
- Integration (Reintegration),
- Renewal,
- Adaptive Reuse (Renovation-Rehabilitation),
- Reconstruction,
- Cleaning, and Relocation

(Kocabişik, 2014; Kurak Açıcı and Konakoğlu, 2019).

In the case of historical buildings, the possibility of adaptive reuse, which is the reapplication of a building that has lost its original function due to changing societal needs over time, is an essential aspect of conservation (Eraybat, 2011; Plevoets and Van Cleempoel, 2011). The purpose of adaptive reuse is to preserve and pass on values such as the historical, aesthetic, and originality of the cultural heritage (Ahunbay, 2013). In this context, the primary aim of conservation is to revitalize the structure with a new function, considering both the historical values it carries and its surroundings as a whole (Yaldız and Asatekin, 2016). In a historically reused building, the key factors influencing design include the preservation of all data reflecting the building's history (Kuban, 2000). Restoring buildings without losing their original identity, assigning them a suitable new function, and ensuring they thrive and pass on to future generations is a critical aspect of conservation work.

Re-functionalization and Examples of Re-functionalized Churches

Historical buildings are works that provide information about a society's past history, reflect its culture, and offer traces of the architectural style and characteristics of the period they belong to. Therefore, learning from the past, benefiting from experience, serving as an example for the future, and passing them on as documentation to future generations imposes an important responsibility to protect these works, which bear the marks of the past (Aydın and Yaldız, 2010). The concept of preservation is regarded as an effort to connect a society's past experiences with its future. Preservation, which directly intervenes with cultural heritage (Feilden, 1982), is expressed as a necessary measure to sustain buildings and structures with historical or artistic value (Hasol, 1988; cited in Yalaz and Yaldız, 2020).

Transmitting the traces of the past to the future is not an easy task. Historical buildings often face destruction and disappearance due to neglect and natural disasters. Therefore, the preservation of historical buildings is essential, though due to financial constraints and other factors, it is not always possible to preserve all structures. For buildings deemed worth preserving, there are specific preservation methods available. These include consolidation, reintegration, renewal (adapting to new functions), reconstruction, cleaning, and relocation. One of the most preferred preservation methods is assigning a new function to historical buildings, which connects them with both the past and the future as cultural and historical heritage. The change in function of historical buildings is considered a contemporary preservation method for protecting the structure (Ahunbay, 2009).

In the process of adaptive reuse, the goal is to transfer historical buildings and sites with cultural heritage value to future

generations, ensure cultural continuity, and enhance the contribution of these structures and areas to the economic and cultural environment. It also aims to beautify the existing environment and meet the needs of the city. Such an approach is considered a necessary application for urban development (Gazi and Boduroğlu, 2015). By preserving historical buildings with their original qualities, their destruction due to social change can be prevented. Thus, the cultural continuity of the heritage is ensured by passing these historical buildings on to future generations (Yalçinkaya et al., 2019). Through restoration work, the reuse of these structures and the application of new functions can ensure their preservation and repair, enabling them to be passed on to future generations (Aras, 2020).

This study aims to evaluate the adaptive reuse of the Haydarpaşa Mosque in the Surlarıçi area of Nicosia, with the goal of preserving the building's original form while assigning it a new function. Examples of adaptive reuse of churches have been observed. The study includes information on the changing functions of the building from past to present and its new function. There are successful examples of adaptive reuse of churches around the world. To support the purpose of the article, three examples of adaptive reuse are provided. In these examples, the original architectural style of historical churches has been preserved without altering their form and design. Among the new functions assigned to these buildings are libraries, mosques, and exhibition spaces.

Examples of Re-functionalised Historic Buildings

A. Surp Vortvots Vorodman Church - İstanbul

Functions Received ;

- Church
- Warehouse
- Chain and Rope Factory
- Shelter
- Culture Centre

Today, the architectural elements of the building were preserved during the restoration process and it is used as a cultural centre.

Surp vortvots vorodman church, exterior photos (Hızır, 2012)

Surp vortvots vorodman church, interior photos (Hızır, 2012)

B. Aya Dimitros Church (Ortaköy Church Mosque)- İstanbul

Functions Received ;

- Church
- Mosque
- Warehouse
- Mosque

After 24 years of inactivity, the church mosque was restored between 2007 and 2009. Today; it has been re-functionalised and serves as a mosque.

Condition of ortaköy church mosque before restoration (KVKBKA,2008)

Interior view of ortaköy church mosque, east facade (Giray Küçük ,2015)

C. Chiesa di S.Maurizio- Italy

Functions Received ;

- Church
- Museum and Exhibition Area

The structure was designed with a single-space perception and its function was assigned according to the space. Following its original use as a "Church" the building was repurposed as a "Museum and Area" without altering its original architectural features.

Exterior and interior photos of chiesa di S. maurizio (E. Fakıbaba archive)

Historical Cultural Heritage Haydarpaşa Mosque (St. Cathrine Church) and Architectural Features

Historical buildings that have survived from the past to the present have undergone changes in their functions over time. One such historical building, the Haydarpaşa Mosque, has come to life with new functional purposes as an immovable cultural heritage. These

structures, which serve as mirrors of our past, transmit the culture of past generations to the future. Therefore, the new functions assigned to these buildings, along with maintenance and restoration, enable them to endure for centuries. Of course, alongside well-maintained structures, there are also dilapidated buildings that have either not survived or have only partially endured to the present day. The adaptive reuse, repairs, and maintenance carried out to preserve our past and culture contribute to the cultural heritage of a country, passed down from generation to generation. As a society, we must ensure this heritage lives on for future generations and set an example. In this study, we observed the various functions the examined building has undergone over time, the functions it currently hosts, and we evaluated the question, "What would happen if it were assigned a different new function?"

Haydarpaşa Mosque (Church of St Katerina)

The Haydarpaşa Mosque is a Catholic religious structure that prominently displays Gothic style features, second only to the Selimiye Mosque in terms of its Gothic characteristics. It has been described by historian Sir Harry Luke as the most elegant and perfect Gothic building in Cyprus (Manga, 2014). In 1918, George Jeffery referred to the Haydar Paşa Mosque as the second most important architectural monument in Nicosia (Jeffery, 1918). This church is also known as the "Bishop's Church" because, while the Selimiye Mosque (St. Sophia Cathedral) was the royal church, the Haydar Paşa Mosque (St. Catherine Church) belonged to the bishopric and is located right next to the Archbishop's Palace. It was built during the Lusignan period in the 14th century. After the conquest of Cyprus, a minaret, mihrab, and pulpit were added, and the building was named after Haydar Paşa, one of the commanders of the Ottoman army.

It's functional features are as follows;

- Firstly, after the religious function with the church structure, it hosted people with the mosque activity as a religious function again.
- In the 1950s, it took a different function as a Marriage Office.
- It was restored between 1986-1991 and used as a mosque function again as Haydar Pasha Mosque.
- After 1991, the building was re-functionalised for art activities. Today, the building is used as a museum and art gallery (Yüksel,2019,p.46). (Figure 6)

Figure 2: Haydarpaşa mosque, art activity function (Yüksel, 2019)

Figure 3: Haydarpaşa mosque (Yüceer, 2012)

a) Architectural Characteristics

Built in the 14th century during the Lusignan period, the building, which is a Catholic church of gothic architecture, was built under the name of St. Cathrine.

- There are long and narrow Gothic windows between the legs narrowing upwards.
- The upper parts of the windows are decorated with geometric patterns made of plaster.
- The building is 17 m long, 8 m wide and 12 m high. [2]
- It has a single nave and the ceiling has a four-part rib vault. [2]
- The ceiling of the five-sided apse next to the nave is supported by six ribs. [2]
- There are buttresses with a trapezoidal cross-section on the outer surface of the building and it has a wavy appearance on the outer surface. [2]
- There are relatively long and narrow windows between the buttresses. The windows have stone lattices and only the west façade has an oculus instead of stone lattice windows. [2] [3]
- The fine stone workmanship of the south gate and the reliefs of the Lusignan coats of arms on the door jamb are remarkable. The west gate is larger and has the same architecture; its jamb is decorated with rose and dragon motifs. The northern entrance is simpler, decorated with reliefs of a naked woman holding a fish on her elbows and a dragon. [4]

Figure 4 : St Catherine's cathedral plan (Manga, 2014)

Taneri & Kahya (2022) note in the *Restoration Yearbook* that the church displays a construction technique not seen in other Gothic structures in the region on its exterior walls. The building features narrow, long windows on its northern and southern walls. Inside, the vaulted system rises on slender and elegant columns. Two light windows, approximately eight meters high, are adorned with richly detailed surrounds at their peaks. The delicate friezes on the windows have managed to survive to this day. The decorations above the windows contain geometric shapes. The vaults are constructed from limestone blocks arranged in a staggered manner. Between the ribbed arches, these stones are filled with a relatively light filling material. On the eastern wall of the building, there is an entrance door with a frame carefully carved and decorated with leaf carvings, and above it, a small round window. The central columns on either side of the door are made of white marble. Among the decorative elements on the frame of the eastern door, roses and dragon heads are particularly striking. The southern door also features similar patterns and designs, along with various Lusignan symbols and emblems (Figure 4).

Figure 5: Haydar Pasha Mosque south façade main entrance door (Taneri 2022)

An interesting feature unique to this church is the presence of an intermediate floor located above the altar, which is of the same size as the altar itself. This intermediate floor shares the same vaulted system and spans the full length of the church. Most likely, this space was divided into two separate levels with a wooden floor. The lower level has a pointed arch and opens into the church through a large window. The upper level, on the other hand, has two rectangular windows on the exterior walls. Access to the lower level

was through a door that connected to the monastic buildings, which no longer exist today. The exact use and purpose of this level and the second floor remain unclear. The lower level was likely used for storing and displaying sacred relics, or perhaps solely for observing religious ceremonies. This section was abandoned with the building's conversion into a mosque. During research and on-site observation-based documentation, it was found that four windows at ground level on the north and south facades of the mosque are later additions. These windows were not mentioned in George Jeffery's 1918 book. Furthermore, the architectural drawings of the church in his book support this observation (Figures 5 and 6). It is believed that these windows were added shortly after Cyprus came under Ottoman rule in 1571, when the building was converted into a mosque in 1573 (Figure 7) (Taneri & Kahya, 2022:89-91).

Figures 6 and 7: Architectural drawings of the Haydar Pasha Mosque (Jeffery 1918: 18, 94)

Figure 8: Haydar Pasha Mosque, which was opened later windows (Taneri 2022)

The Haydarpaşa Mosque, located in the walled city area of Nicosia, which serves as the central point of the historical fabric and houses important historical structures, has been evaluated for the possibility of being refunctionalized with its current function. In order to assess this, local residents in the area have been surveyed for information. The number of people who participated in the survey and their education levels are provided below (Table 1). The percentages of the responses were calculated using Excel, and the satisfaction levels were determined with graphical results. A total of 30 individuals participated in the survey.

Table 1. Education level, number and ratio of the respondents

Education Level	Participant (number of people)	Rate (%)
Bachelor's Degree	18	60,00
Master's Degree	11	36,67
Ph.D.	1	3,33

FINDINGS

The Haydarpaşa Art Gallery, also known as Haydarpaşa Mosque, has served different functions over time and has hosted various activities. According to survey results, the public became aware of these functions through the services provided. The majority agreed that the architectural features of the building's original function as a church have been largely preserved to the present day. Survey findings also revealed that individuals who believed the church should have remained unchanged over time supported the idea of preserving the structure in its original form. The survey results further indicated that maintaining the building's current function would be beneficial for Cyprus and its cultural heritage. Regarding the potential reassignment of a new function to the

structure, 90% of the respondents preferred its transformation into a library, while 83% supported the idea of converting it into a museum.

The historical church, now known as Haydarpaşa Mosque, most recently functioned as the Haydarpaşa Art Gallery. To assess public satisfaction with its latest function and to evaluate the possibility of another functional transformation, a survey was conducted.

Participants in the survey were asked to indicate their level of agreement with each statement by selecting one of the following options:

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

The satisfaction levels regarding the building’s current function were analyzed based on the percentage distribution of responses across the categories 'Strongly Disagree,' 'Disagree,' 'Agree,' and 'Strongly Agree' (Table 2).

Table 2. Satisfaction level of the structure's current function

Question Numbers	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
1	3	17	3	7
2	0	7	1	22
3	7	22	0	1
4	4	22	1	3
5	2	11	1	16
6	1	15	1	13
7	1	13	1	15

Among the possibilities for acquiring a new function, the survey included four options. During the evaluation, the response categories 'Strongly Disagree,' 'Disagree,' 'Agree,' and 'Strongly Agree' were considered (Table 3).

Table 3. Value of the structure's potential to adopt a new function

Function	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Museum	2	1	2	25
Library	1	1	1	27
Boutique Store	2	28	-	-
Gift Shop	2	27	-	1
Restaurant	2	28	-	-
Cafe	-	27	-	3
Tourism Counselor Office	-	21	-	9
Architecture Office	2	21	2	5
Daily Accommodation	2	27	-	1

In the evaluation of new functional possibilities, the provided options were analyzed, and the corresponding graphical representation is presented below.

DISCUSSION

The process of giving new functions to structures for the preservation of historical monuments and transferring them to future generations, with a focus on the restoration and protection of the building through its functional use, has been examined in the study of the Haydarpaşa Art Gallery, also known as the Haydarpaşa Mosque. It is known that the building has undergone different functions over time, and its most recent function is that it is currently not serving the public and remains closed. However, it is known that the re-functionalization of the building is an important step for intervening in potential damages and carrying out protection works, as the building continues to function.

The Haydarpaşa structure, with its most recent function, not serving and being closed, is considered a negative situation according to the findings from our research. When a building remains closed, it can lead to deterioration over time, and the loss of the cultural reflection, historical value, identity of the building, and its potential transmission to future generations. Gazi and Boduroğlu (2015) state that "re-functionalization can be considered as a necessary practice to ensure that structures and areas with historical value reach future generations, maintain cultural continuity, increase the contribution of structures and areas to the economic and cultural environment by re-evaluating them, and beautify the existing environment to meet the needs of the city." While the positive aspects of re-functioning buildings are evident, the study also revealed some opinions suggesting that the function of the building should remain unchanged, it should be preserved as a church, and its original state should be passed on to future generations. Such viewpoints express a desire to understand how culture existed in the past and see its transformation. As for re-functioning, it is known that the likelihood of choosing a library or museum function is high, as it would cause minimal damage to the architectural features of the building. This is due to the fact that the building reflects our culture, and there are ideas that it should remain in its original form with these two new functions. However, there are complaints about the loss of motifs and decorations when the building functioned as a mosque, given that the original architectural elements of the building have not survived to the present day.

The re-functionalization, preservation, and transmission of historical buildings, as well as the continuation of our culture, have many positive aspects. The fact that the cultural practices of the past serve as an example and can still be felt in current architecture is exciting. I believe that while re-functioning buildings, we must ensure that their original elements are not destroyed, but rather preserved. In doing so, we show respect for the culture of the people who lived in the past, and we also ensure that the buildings we construct today reflect our culture in a way that does not distort it, preserving our way of life for future generations.

CONCLUSION

Historical buildings are among our important works that reflect the culture, lifestyle, and architectural style of our past to the present day. The rich historical structures of Cyprus are also present today. The capital, Nicosia, has played a central role in the formation of historical buildings and has gained significant importance in enriching the urban and historical fabric in the center. The St. Catherine Church, which reflects the Gothic architectural features of the Lusignan period in the 14th century, currently serves as the Haydarpaşa Art Gallery, having undergone several transformations from its previous function and name as Haydarpaşa Mosque. This building has survived to the present day through multiple functions. Due to events such as natural disasters and wars, the structure has been repaired and adapted with the resources of the time. Described as the second most important architectural monument in Nicosia, the building was originally constructed as a church and later transformed to include a minaret, mihrab, and pulpit according to the needs of the period. It was then named after Haydar Paşa, an Ottoman army commander. Since 1951, the building has served various purposes, including as the Marriage Bureau, a storage facility, and, currently, as an Art Gallery and

Exhibition Hall. Throughout its different functions, Haydarpaşa Mosque has continued to serve and reach the present day. Some original architectural elements of the structure have not survived to the present day due to natural disasters, wars, and other factors, resulting in the destruction and damage of certain parts. During its transformations, repairs were made, and in the renovation process in accordance with Islamic practices, decorative elements in the church's interior walls were covered with plaster, which means some original architectural features are no longer visible. Some additions were also made to the building, including new windows on the ground floors of the north and south facades, which are considered to be part of later modifications

Many of our historical buildings have been destroyed over time and have either not survived to the present day or have only parts of them preserved and protected. Efforts are being made to pass our historical structures on to the future. There are institutions and organizations dedicated to restoration and conservation. In order to carry our buildings into the future, it has been considered necessary to regularly maintain and restore them, and to assign new functions to them. By intervening in a timely manner, the preserved buildings are now taking on different functions according to their architectural features. Historical buildings that serve as libraries, museums, accommodations, and exhibition halls hold an important place in our culture. As seen in the examples examined, restoration work has been carried out to ensure the transfer of cultural heritage to the future. After restoration, the structures continue to serve the public with their new functions, thus ensuring that they are passed on to future generations.

The structure in our research, however, is currently not in use after having taken on various functions. Based on the findings, there were participants who were unaware of the possibility of the structure adopting new functions, while others believed that the building should be preserved in its original form as a church. The option of the structure continuing to serve as an Art Gallery was also positively received by the participants. Regarding the possibility of assigning new functions, it was observed from the data that the most preferred options for the structure's future were museum and library functions. It is believed that for the structures to serve the public, maintenance and restoration should be done in a timely manner, and this will reflect our culture in its most authentic form and facilitate the flow of knowledge.

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